

Drought resistance

Dryland rice selections for drought-prone areas of West Bengal, India

N. C. Basu Raychaudhuri, Rice Research Station, Bankura, India

Drought is the most serious problem for rainfed dryland rice areas of West Bengal, India's leading rice-growing state. New semidwarf varieties have made little impact because they cannot tolerate moisture stress.

Rice areas in the 2 worst affected districts, Bankura and Purulia, are about 380,000 and 230,000 ha. A single crop of rainfed rice is the main livelihood of the farmers; dryland rice accounts for more than 60% of the rice lands. Among the main causes of low yields are short and uneven rainfall distribution, undulating land, and poor soil moisture retention.

Work on dryland rice improvement was undertaken at Bankura and Purulia. A number of field screening tests using cultivars obtained through the International Rice Testing Program (IRTP) were followed by yield potential tests. For 2 years (1976 and 1977), more than 200 dryland rice cultivars from different

Promising dryland cultivars for the drought-prone areas of West Bengal, India.

Designation	Origin	Maturity (days)	Plant ht (cm)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Drought reaction ^a
B9c-Md-3	Indonesia	99	96	4.1	3
IR2061-522-6-9	IRRI	104	114	3.7	3
IET1444	India	103	92	3.6	3
CR141-192	India	100	105	3.5	1
CR125-17	India	89	88	3.5	3
Se. 302-G	Senegal	90	82	3.5	3
CR143-2-2	India	102	95	3.4	3
DV110	Bangladesh	105	136	3.4	3
RC7046	India	102	132	3.3	3
Panke	India	101	142	3.3	1
ARC7060	India	89	146	3.3	1
Se. 322 B19	Senegal	89	80	3.2	1
FH109	India	103	99	3.2	3
Brown Gora	India	93	132	3.2	1
CTG1516	Bangladesh	100	140	2.9	1

^aAt reproductive stage. 1 = none to slight effect of stress, 3 = moderate effect of stress (leaf tip drying up to 3/4 length of leaves).

countries were tested in duplicate sets in the two districts on a typical coarse sandy loam soil with poor moisture retention.

Visual scoring of drought resistance and recovery and effects of drought on growth and yield components were periodically recorded according to the IRRI Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

More than 50% of the entries, mostly

tall traditional types, were tolerant of drought. After rigorous screening, 24 early-maturing (105 days) and 24 medium-maturing types (106–125 days) were selected and tested for yield potential. The most promising (see table) have been further tested in adaptive trials and minikit plots in different locations, and results are encouraging. ■

The line source sprinkler: a new research tool for drought screening

J. C. O'Toole and D. W. Puckridge, Agronomy Department, International Rice Research Institute

A new research technique, the line source sprinkler, was evaluated at IRRI for use in drought resistance screening in the 1979 dry season. Figure 1 illustrates the field installation, which consists of full-circle sprinklers spaced at intervals of 6.1 m (20-ft pipe section). The system produces a linear decrease in the amount of water applied with distance away from the line (Fig. 2). Also shown in Figure 2 are some crop responses to varying amounts of applied irrigation water.

1. Schematic of the field layout of sprinklers in the source sprinkler technique.

2. Linear decrease in water applied and corresponding crop response, i.e. dry weight of tops and visual drought score after 47 and 61 days.

Although space restrictions prohibit the illustration of all the variables measured, we found a high correlation of such responses as dry matter accumulation, leaf area index, plant height, leaf water potential, drought resistance score, yield, and yield components with the water applied. That finding illustrates the technique's usefulness in research where water is a primary variable. The line source sprinkler may be used at a particular growth stage such as the very sensitive flowering stage. We plan to use it to develop a drought screening method that will be sensitive to yield and percentage sterility.

The line source sprinkler technique was developed by Dr. R. J. Hanks and

associates at Utah State University, USA. It should be particularly useful in climates where a distinct dry season allows its use without rainfall. If properly used, the technique would shorten to one or two dry seasons the

many years of multilocal testing, which are costly and involve the problem of interpreting the complex effects of natural droughts. Interested rice scientists may contact the authors for further details. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Adverse soils tolerance

Zinc deficiency – a new problem for irrigated rice in Bangladesh

Animesh C. Roy and A. K. M. Shahjahan, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh

The introduction of modern rice varieties has intensified rice cultivation in Bangladesh, particularly in areas with dry-season irrigation. Newer BRRI varieties adapted to various locations and seasons have changed the total cropping patterns substantially in irrigated rice lands. Additional irrigation facilities and projects have further intensified rice production. But the intensive wetland rice cultivation has also brought about new soil problems.

Because of several field reports on the poor performance of the modern varieties in some irrigated areas of Bangladesh, we conducted a preliminary survey to

identify the actual field problems of rice cultivation in major rice-growing areas of Bangladesh in the 1978–79 aus, aman, and boro seasons. In some irrigated lands, particularly in the alkaline zone, we observed a new nutritional problem associated with continuous wetland conditions.

In large areas of alkaline soils in the Ganges-Kobadak Project in north-western Bangladesh with year-round irrigation, rice plants were characterized by stunted growth, poor root development, and in severe cases, rusty brown spots on the leaves. Similar symptoms were also observed in Faridpur, Kishoreganj, Chittagong, Barisal, Comilla, and Dacca districts. Suspecting zinc deficiency, we collected soil and plant samples for laboratory analysis. The results confirmed our field observations (see table).

Soil and plant analyses data on some selected samples with suspected zinc deficiency. Bangladesh Rice Research Institute.

Location	District	pH	Soil characteristics		Plant zinc (ppm)	Variety
			Organic matter (%)	0.05N HCl ^a extractable zinc (ppm)		
DND project	Dacca	7.40	n.a.	0.48	21.1	IR8
CIP	Comilla	7.40	1.72	0.52	12.5	IR8
Gournadi	Barisal	6.85	2.29	0.83	n.a.	local
BRRI station	Rajshahi	8.00	1.05	0.00	18.6	IRTN line
Kanaipur	Faridpur	7.70	1.76	0.08	n.a.	IR8
Mohanandapur	Faridpur	7.80	1.64	0.07	12.5	IR8
Kaijuri	Faridpur	7.90	2.07	0.10	14.5	IR8
Sajekupa	Jessore	7.40	2.10	0.28	15.7	IR8, BR1
Amla	Kushtia	7.40	2.48	0.13	9.6	BR3, BR1
Sandwip	Chittagong	7.95	1.50	0.95	19.6	IR8
Jhenaida	Jessore	7.78	2.27	0.14	28.0	IR8, BR3
Maria	Kishoreganj	6.90	2.00	2.08	18.8	IR8
Gangail	Kishoreganj	7.20	1.81	2.48	19.7	BR3, IR8
Santhia	Pabna	7.85	2.25	0.10	20.1	BR4
BAU	Mymensingh	7.40	1.98	1.46	15.9	IR8

^aExtractable soil zinc was estimated by the Katyal and Ponnampuruma method. n.a. = not analyzed.